

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 9th – 15th November 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

November 12, 2020 (NEJM)

An mRNA Vaccine against SARS-CoV-2 — Preliminary Report

Lisa A. Jackson, Evan J. Anderson, Nadine G. Rouphael et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2022483>

Two injections of mRNA-1273, a lipid nanoparticle-encapsulated mRNA-based vaccine produced in collaboration with the NIAID that encodes the SARS-CoV2 spike protein, induced anti-SARS-CoV-2 immune responses in all participants, and no trial-limiting safety concerns were identified in the phase 1 trial. These findings support further development of this vaccine.

November 12, 2020 (The Lancet)

Ethnicity and clinical outcomes in COVID-19: A systematic analysis

Shirley Sze, Daniel Pan, Clareece R. Nevill et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100630>

The authors performed a systematic review and meta-analysis to explore the relationship between ethnicity and clinical outcomes in COVID-19. After analysing data of more than 18 million patients from 50 studies, they found that individuals of Black and Asian ethnicity are at increased risk of COVID-19 infection compared to White individuals and that Asians may be at a higher risk of ICU admission and death. These findings are of critical public health importance in informing interventions to reduce morbidity and mortality amongst ethnic minority groups.

November 12, 2020 (JAMA Int. Med.)

Assessment of SARS-CoV-2 RNA Test Results Among Patients Who Recovered From COVID-19 With Prior Negative Results

Flora Marzia Liotti, Giulia Menchinelli, Simona Marchetti et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2020.7570>

This study examines positive rt-PCR nasal-oropharyngeal swab results from patients who recovered from COVID-19 with prior negative results. This study highlights that many patients who recovered from COVID-19 may be still positive (albeit at lower levels) for SARS-CoV-2 RNA, but only a minority of the patients may carry a replicating SARS-CoV-2 in the respiratory tract. Further studies are needed to verify whether such patients can transmit the virus.

November 11, 2020 (Int. J of Stroke)

Stroke in COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis

Stefania Nannoni, Rosa de Groot, Steven Bell et. al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1747493020972922>

COVID-19 is not just a respiratory disease. Here, the authors aimed to characterize the incidence, risk factors, clinical–radiological manifestations, and outcome of COVID-19-associated stroke. They found that acute cerebrovascular diseases are not uncommon in patients with COVID-19, especially in those with severe and have pre-existing vascular risk factors. The pattern of large vessel occlusion and multi-territory infarcts suggests that cerebral thrombosis and/or thromboembolism could be possible causative pathways for the disease.

November 10, 2020 (JAMA)

Gastrointestinal Complications in Critically Ill Patients With and Without COVID-19

Mohamad El Moheb, Leon Naar, Mathias A. Christensen et. al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2020.19400>

This cohort study compares the incidence of gastrointestinal complications (transaminitis, ileus, Ogilvie syndrome, mesenteric ischemia) among critically ill patients with COVID-19 vs non–COVID-19–induced acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) at a single US academic hospital between March and May 2020. Although limited to a single centre and by the unavailability of inflammatory markers to use for matching, the authors found a higher rate of gastrointestinal complications, including mesenteric ischemia, in critically ill patients with COVID-19 suggesting a distinct phenotype for COVID-19 compared with conventional ARDS.

B. Science and Engineering

November 12, 2020 (Frontiers in Physics)

Trend Analysis of COVID-19 Based on Network Topology Description

Jun Zhu, Yangqianzi Jiang, Tianrui Li et al.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2020.564061>

In this study, the trend of the epidemic situation of COVID-19 is analyzed based on the analysis method for network topology. Combining with the sliding window method, the dynamic networks with different topologies for each window are built to consider the relationship of the data on different days. Then the static statistical features on network topologies at different times are extracted during the dynamic evolution of complex networks. It is found that if the value of the trend function tends to decrease, then the epidemic will be effectively controlled.

November 12, 2020 (Frontiers in Physics)

Can Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs Affect the Interaction Between Receptor Binding Domain of SARS-COV-2 Spike and the Human ACE2 Receptor? A Computational Biophysical Study

Lenin A. Gonzalez-Paz, Carla A. Lossada, Francelys V. Fernandez Materan et al.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2020.587606>

These researchers carried out an exhaustive computational biophysical study of various NSAIDs targeting the RBD-ACE2 complex using multiple comparative analysis of docking and molecular dynamics. Only the Ibuprofen (Propionic acid derivative), Aspirin (Salicylate), and the Acetaminophen (p-aminophenol derivative) had a thermodynamically favourable docking with the interface of the RBD-ACE2 complex. Their results point to Ibuprofen is an NSAID that has the highest probability of generating a disturbance in the stability of the RBD-ACE2 complex. This remains only a theory and requires experiments to demonstrate clinically relevant interaction.

November 11, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Network interventions for managing the COVID-19 pandemic and sustaining economy

Akihiro Nishi, George Dewey, Akira Endo et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2014297117>

The authors use agent-based simulations of a network-based susceptible–exposed–infectious–recovered (SEIR) model to investigate two network intervention strategies for mitigating the spread of transmission while maintaining economic activities. They assume that people engage in group activities in multiple sectors where they interact with others in the same group and potentially become infected. The simulation results show that the dividing groups' strategy greatly reduces transmission, and the joint implementation of the two strategies could effectively control the spread of transmission.

November 10, 2020 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

The interplay of movement and spatiotemporal variation in transmission degrades pandemic control

Nicholas Kortessis, Margaret W. Simon, Michael Barfield et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2018286117>

Kortessis et al use a susceptible-infectious-recovered (SIR) model for two coupled populations to make the conceptual point that asynchronous, variable local control, together with movement between populations, elevates long-term regional R_t and cumulative cases. For effective pandemic mitigation strategies, models must include both spatiotemporal heterogeneity in transmission and movement.

October 20, 2020 (Chaos, Solitons & Fractals)

Is spread of COVID-19 a chaotic epidemic?

Andrew Jones & Nikolay Strigul

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2020.110376>

Yes, it is. Traditional compartmental epidemiological models demonstrated limited ability to predict the scale and dynamics of the epidemic. To gain a deeper understanding of its behaviour, they turn to chaotic dynamics. They hypothesize that the unpredictability of the pandemic could be a fundamental property if the disease spread is a chaotic dynamical system. They conclude that the COVID-19 epidemic demonstrates chaotic behaviour, which should be taken into account by public policymakers. They stress that the scale and behaviour of the epidemic are essentially unpredictable due to the properties of chaotic systems.

October 22, 2020 (Applied Mathematical Modelling)

Global analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic using simple epidemiological models

Jose Enrique Amaro, Jeremie Dudouet, Jose Nicholas Orce et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apm.2020.10.019>

Several analytical models have been developed in this work to describe the evolution of fatalities arising from coronavirus COVID-19 worldwide. The Death or 'D' model is a simplified version of the SIR (susceptible-infected-recovered) compartment model, which allows for the transmission-dynamics equations to be solved analytically by assuming no recovery. The D-model provides a precise way to characterize the exponential and normal phases of the pandemic evolution. More accurate calculations using the extended SIR or ESIR model and Monte Carlo grid simulations predict similar trends. These results suggest a common pandemic evolution with universal parameters. The fact that the D and ESIR models predict similar results shows that COVID-19 is a highly contagious virus, but that most people become asymptomatic (D model) and eventually recover (ESIR model).

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

November 3, 2020 (Explorations in Economic History)

Disease, downturns, and wellbeing: Economic history and the long-run impacts of COVID-19

Vellore Arthi & John Parman.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2020.101381>

The authors review the evidence on the long term effects on health, labour, and human capital of both historical pandemics (with a focus on the 1918 Influenza Pandemic) and historical recessions (with a focus on the Great Depression). They discuss how past crises can tell us what to look for, what to prepare for, and what data we should collect now.

November 2, 2020 (Journal of Computational Social Science)

Partisan public health: how does political ideology influence support for COVID-19 related misinformation?

Nicholas Francis Havey

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s42001-020-00089-2>

This study analyzes over 4000 tweets related to six misinformation topics about the pandemic: the use of hydroxychloroquine as treatment, the use of bleach as a preventative measure, Bill Gates intentionally causing the virus, the Chinese Communist Party intentionally causing the virus, and the Deep State causing the virus to ruin the economy and threaten President Trump's reelection chances. Pandemic misinformation has been associated with decreased compliance with public health recommendations and evidence from the current pandemic indicates that adherence to public health recommendations is divided. This study suggests that the political and informational polarization fuelled by social media platforms such as Twitter may have serious consequences for public health.

October 17, 2020 (Public Health)

Socio-economic status and COVID-19–related cases and fatalities

R. B. Hawkins, E. J. Charles, J. H. Mehaffey.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2020.09.016>

The authors quantify the associations between socio-economic status and COVID-19–related cases and mortality in the U.S. They use nationwide COVID-19 data at the county level that were paired with the Distressed Communities Index (DCI) and its component metrics of socio-economic status. This cohort included 1,089,999 cases and 62,298 deaths in 3127 counties for a case fatality rate of 5.7%. They conclude that lower education levels and greater proportion of black residents are strongly associated with higher rates of both COVID-19 cases and fatalities.